

INSTABILITY AND COLLAPSE OF SANDWICH SHELLS REPRESENTING A/C WING SKINS

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SUMMARY

Instability failure mode of nearly cylindrical sandwich shell was investigated by theoretical calculation. Finite Element Analysis and finally verified by two test specimens. During the test, information regarding snap-through, buckling mode and post buckling behaviour were collected. These indications were obtained by using the F/S method.

Keywords: Instability, collapse, sandwich, shell, skin, torsion, experiment, force stiffness.

INTRODUCTION

The instability and the failure mode of nearly cylindrical sandwich shells, loaded in torsion, were investigated by theoretical calculation, Finite Element Analysis and verified by three parametric test specimens. Limited studies on composite wing boxes have been reported (Ref. 1-3), but they are all for solid laminate skins and none for thin composite sandwich shell skins. The purpose of this work was to develop a method for the analysis for the prediction of instability (buckling) and collapse (failure) of lightweight sandwich shells. The results are to be used in the design of GA (general aviation) structures. In order to achieve this goal it was necessary to answer the following questions:

1. How do experimental results correlate with theoretical calculations and with Finite Element Analysis?
2. How do imperfections in cylindrical geometry affect the buckling and failure mode?
3. How does the ratio $\left(\frac{R}{t_{eq}}\right)$ between shell curvature (R) and sandwich equivalent

thickness (t_{eq}), affect the instability and the failure behavior?

$t_{eq} = \sqrt[3]{6H^2t_f}$, H is the core thickness and t_f is the sandwich face thickness.

4. Does the sandwich fail in a catastrophic manner or in a progressive collapse process?

Analysis Prediction

Theoretical calculations were made to provide initial prediction of the failure. Buckling of the wing section as presented in Figure 1, was made assuming buckling of simply supported circular cylinder in torsion and using the theoretical solution of Batdorf, Stein and Schildcrout (Ref. 7). Finite Element models were analyzed using Nastran Eigen Value Solution 105 (Ref. 8).

Figure 1: Scheme of the analytical procedure

Figure 2: (a) Test setup of the wing section element test used in the experiment.

(b) Schematic cross section of the wing showing the spars and the skins.

Experimental work

In order to answer the questions above, three test specimens were built and tested. The test specimens consist of 1.5 m segments of a wing torsion box, as shown in Figure 2a. The box is attached through 4 attachment fittings at both ends to loading plates, to minimize the warping effect which occurs as an effect of the torsion loading. The hydraulic actuators, working in tension as a force couple, apply torsion moment on the specimen. The upper and lower surfaces are both cylindrical ($R = 1000 \text{ mm}$) with the difference that the upper is almost a perfect cylinder while the lower deviates from the cylinder shape, as can be seen in Figure 2b. The skins are made of sandwiches of polymethacrylimide foam core and $\pm 45^\circ$ Carbon Epoxy fabric plies. The three specimens are identical excluding the core thickness; the first has a thick core throughout, the second has a thick core at the bottom skin and thin core at the

upper skin and the third test specimen has thin core throughout. During the test, in real time, an array of strain gauges were used to supply information regarding snap-through, buckling mode and post buckling behavior. These observations were obtained by using the F/S (force stiffness) method (Ref. 4-6). The first test specimen (thick) failed suddenly at the loading fitting just a little before buckling occurred. The second test specimen, with thicker core thickness at the lower skin, was built to investigate the failure at the upper skin. The upper skin collapsed due to flattening. The third test specimen (thinner) collapsed progressively at the lower skin (Figure 3).

Results Discussion

Using the F/S method, buckling and snap-through can be observed during the test. The results are summarized in Table 1. The test results are in good correlation with both the Finite Element and theoretical predictions. The results for each specimen are for the tested skin.

First Specimen: It was shown by S.G. readings, through F/S method, that the buckling initiation was on the lower surface. Failure was predicted to be 7.13 ton-meter (Table 1).

Figure 3: Photo of the collapsed lower skin of the third specimen

Second specimen: Several snap through events recorded for the upper skin at early stage of the loading. Adding this to a deeper investigation of the strains readings, it was realized that the observed snap through event is related to a Flattening phenomena. The progress of Flattening is described schematically in Figure 4. As seen, the torsion moment acting on the specimen reacts as pure shear on the skin which can be represented as a force couple. The tension force along the diagonal of the skin creates a tension band which attends to flatten the

convex surface. This effect of Flattening cause local bending which increase the compression stresses on the outer face of the sandwich. These stresses happen to be in the same direction as the compression diagonal. Due to this increase, the compression margin of the composite is addressed.

Third Specimen: The F/S plots in Figure 5 show buckling on the lower surface. Like the first test, during the loading a snap-through event was recorded by the F/S plots shown in Figure 6. These F/S signatures before failure suggest to the existence of post buckling behaviour. This specimen having $R/t_{eq} = 259$ (higher then the first $R/t_{eq} = 188$) passed through a number of snap-through events.

Figure 4: Schematic description of the Flattening progress

Figure 5: Quiet collapse of the mid band shown by strain values and Force Stiffness curves for the lower skin of the 3rd specimen.

Figure 6: Snap through illustration on the lower skin of the first test specimen

Table 1: Summary of theoretical calculations, analysis and test results

#	description	Theoretical cylinder ($10^4\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$)	FE Eigen value ($10^4\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$)	F/S Prediction	Test Result ($10^4\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$)	Failure mode
1	Thicker core $R/t_{eq} = 188$	7.94	6.1	7.13	5.73	End rib fitting
2	Thin and thick core	-	7.5	-	3.98*	Flattening
3	Thinner core $R/t_{eq} = 259$	4.4	3.34	4.0	3.75	Buckling

*premature failure due to manufacture defects at the core-face bonding

Conclusions

The results are encouraging; despite the imperfection and the fragility of the sandwich shells, the maximum theoretical and FE predicted loads were similar to those obtained experimentally. The premature collapse of the second specimen due to the Flattening effect occurred because of manufacture defects. Despite these defects, the Flattening should be interpreted as evidence for a critical failure mode. A knock down factor of 0.8 from the allowable stress should be taken for Flattening effect. This behavior will be verified by further testing.

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